

The Impact of Multimedia Teaching Aids on Primary School Students' Learning Motivation in China

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of multimedia teaching aids on the learning motivation of primary school students in China, focusing on the three dimensions of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and task value. Employing a quantitative research approach, this research was conducted with 144 fifth-grade students, aged 9 to 12, who came from Anhui Province. The subjects were randomly allocated into four different groups, such as video, audio, interactive whiteboards, and gamified tools. During the two-week experiment, all groups learned the same instructional content through assigned tools. This study collected quantitative data through pre-test and post-test questionnaires. The results showed that interactive whiteboards are the most effective in improving learning interest, participation, and perception of the importance of learning. Video tools are effective in increasing the sense of task value.

The research results show that the use of appropriate multimedia teaching aids can improve students' learning motivation. This study recommends strengthening teacher multimedia technology training and optimizing resource allocation. In the future, the comprehensive use of multiple multimedia tools and their long-term effects can be further explored, combined with qualitative research methods, to gain a deeper understanding of students' subjective experiences and emotions.

Keywords: multimedia teaching aids, learning motivation, primary education, interactive tools, quantitative analysis

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

With the rapid development of digital technology, rich texts, pictures, videos and internet resources have gradually replaced traditional books and chalk. Multimedia teaching aids have become an important part of the education field and have grabbed the attention of educators. More and more of educators are bringing multimedia teaching aids into the classroom. This new teaching method brings students a more vivid and interactive learning atmosphere (Li et al., 2019). The widespread use of multimedia teaching aids has brought innovation and changes to traditional teaching methods, emphasizing the importance of a dynamic and interactive learning environment. Multimedia teaching aids such as video, audio, animation, graphics and text can be used to stimulate students' enthusiasm and improve student participation. Multimedia teaching aids bring diverse learning resources and reshape teaching methods and the way students participate in learning.

As modern educational technology, multimedia teaching aids can promote learning in various forms and support a personalized, dynamic and inclusive learning environment. However, its effectiveness and role still deserve further exploration. According to the study by Lauc et al. (2020) found that multimedia teaching aids can effectively enhance the positive impact of instant feedback in the learning process, and motivation is directly proportional to learning performance. Many scholars have conducted in-depth research on the application of multimedia teaching aids. Abdulrahman et al. (2020) found that integrating multimedia teaching aids can significantly improve students' motivation and attention. Similarly, Blanco et al. (2024) analyzed the impact of different multimedia teaching aids, including visual tools, digital tools, interactive whiteboards, and artificial intelligence, on student learning outcomes.

Multimedia teaching aids promote the development of educational technology and support each student to obtain a learning experience suitable for them. Especially in China's primary education environment, multimedia education plays an important role. Continuous exploration of the application of multimedia teaching aids in

education can further promote innovation in teaching and learning methods. The purpose of this study is to fill this research gap, study how multimedia teaching aids affect the learning motivation of Chinese primary school students, and provide basic support for future educational practice and research.

1.2 Problem Statement

In teaching practice, multimedia teaching aids are increasingly used in primary school teaching. Teachers use multimedia tools appropriately according to students' needs to stimulate students' desire to explore and creative thinking. However, how and what extent these tools influence learning motivation has not been fully studied. Existing research shows the potential value of multimedia teaching aids in improving learning motivation, but it is mainly concentrated in secondary and higher education, where older students have stronger cognitive abilities and longer attention spans. There are significant differences between primary school students and senior students due to different levels of cognition, limited attention, and motivational needs. Determining the most effective types of multimedia and their impact on learning outcomes for young students has important implications for optimizing educational practice.

Multimedia teaching aids for young learners require thoughtful design to align with their cognitive development. Studies indicate that students in lower grades are still building their cognitive skills and often have shorter attention spans; therefore, they tend to respond more effectively to interactive, visually engaging multimedia suited to their developmental stage (Rachmavita, 2020). Nonetheless, overly entertaining multimedia can sometimes detract from achieving educational objectives (Kalay & Arıkan, 2023). Yu et al. (2022) highlighted the need for tools that not only foster active learning but also support long-term retention through ongoing feedback. Consequently, examining how multimedia aids impact the motivation, engagement, and academic outcomes of primary school students in China is essential to developing more tailored early education strategies.

In daily teaching activities, educators are troubled by how to effectively use multimedia teaching aids to improve teaching effects. They often face challenges when selecting and implementing multimedia instruction. Although multimedia teaching aids can provide a rich and interesting learning experience, students' reactions vary. Younger students may need simpler and more vivid interfaces and learning content due to cognitive limitations. Moreover, teachers lack clear guidance or training in the use of multimedia technologies, making it difficult to effectively integrate these tools into teaching.

This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the impact of various multimedia teaching aids on Chinese primary school students' learning motivation. By identifying specific multimedia types that promote engagement and motivation, this study will provide targeted insights and provide evidence-based data support for educators to help them scientifically select and apply the most suitable multimedia teaching aids for primary school students, thereby improving students' engagement and academic performance.

1.3 Objectives

The purpose of this study is to evaluate and compare the impact of different multimedia teaching aids on primary school students' learning motivation. The specific objectives are:

1. To evaluate the use of multimedia teaching aids and their role in improving learning motivation.
2. To compare the impact of different multimedia teaching aids on learning motivation.
3. To analyze the effects of multimedia teaching aids on stimulating learning enthusiasm.

1.4 Research Questions

The specific research questions are:

1. What type of multimedia teaching aids are most effective in increasing primary school students' learning motivation?
2. How do the most effective multimedia teaching aids specifically impact students' learning outcomes and motivation?
3. What are the differences in learning motivation outcomes when different multimedia tools are used in class ?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

1. The use of multimedia teaching aids positively affects primary school students' learning motivation in China.
2. Different types of multimedia teaching aids have varying levels of effectiveness in enhancing learning motivation, with visual and interactive tools having the most influence.
3. Students exposed to multimedia teaching aids show higher levels of engagement and enthusiasm compared to those taught with traditional methods.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The results of this study will help Chinese educators gain an in-depth understanding of how different types of multimedia teaching aids can effectively improve primary school students' learning motivation. By identifying the most effective multimedia tools, teachers can make more scientific teaching decisions based on these research data and rationally select multimedia tools to use in the classroom to improve student participation and learning performance. At the same time, students will benefit from the effective use of these tools, which can increase motivation and enthusiasm for learning, and ultimately lead to better academic outcomes. The study's findings may also lead to more interactive and high-engagement teaching practices to further enhance students' learning experience.

In addition, this study will provide empirical evidence for the specific impact of multimedia teaching tools on primary school students' learning motivation, especially in the Chinese educational context. The findings can provide educators, policy makers,

and curriculum developers with practical insights into how to effectively implement multimedia tools to enhance learning motivation. As digital education receives increasing attention, this study will also help teachers integrate multimedia teaching aids into primary school curriculum so that the application of technology meets the cognitive development needs of primary school students to promote students' learning motivation and enthusiasm.

1.7 Limitations

This study may face some limitations. First, because it will focus primarily on primary school students in Anhui, China, the findings may limit the generalizability of the results to other regions or educational settings. In addition, each tool has different application and technical requirements, and its effectiveness will be affected by usage skills and student acceptance. Finally, the duration of the study may not have been sufficient to observe the long-term effects of multimedia teaching aids on student motivation, which may limit the scope of conclusions drawn.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Multimedia Teaching Aids & Learning Motivation

Multimedia teaching aids are teaching equipment that uses digital technology to combine multiple media information (images, sounds, text, videos, animations, games) for display and dissemination. Through the design and application of teaching processes and resources, students can more easily understand complex concepts and content, stimulate students' sensory experience, make learning content interesting and vivid, stimulate students' interest in learning, and improve learning efficiency.

Learning motivation is directly related to students' investment, perseverance and sense of achievement, and is the internal driving force for students to participate in the learning process. Motivation is divided into intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation comes from interest in learning and curiosity, while extrinsic motivation comes from grades and external rewards. Research by Lin et al.

(2017) found that motivation levels are positively correlated with academic performance, and students' initiative was affected by autonomy and cognitive ability.

Teachers use multimedia teaching aids to teach, which can create an intuitive and vivid teaching situation for students, which is in line with the characteristics and rules of primary school students' thinking and cognitive development stages. Integrating multimedia teaching aids into the teaching process can not only promote students' independent inquiry and learning, but also promote knowledge understanding.

2.2 Research context and current situation

Many studies have tried various methods to analyze various tools. For example, digital tools and visual tools, to understand how multimedia teaching aids can really improve the quality of teaching and make learning more interesting. Projectors and videos are often used in controlled experiments and pretests because these tools are great for demonstrating how well students retain things and stay motivated. On the other hand, learning using interactive whiteboards or gamified learning tools is sometimes accompanied by classroom observations and interviews to understand student and teacher interactions and maintain learning continuity in the long run. Each method has its advantages. Controlled experiments provide clear, measurable data, while qualitative methods dig deeper into the overall learning process and social interactions (Fajari, 2022).

Mai (2019) examined the intrinsic and extrinsic learning motivations of learning behavior through data statistical analysis, revealing that the use of multimedia teaching aids has a positive impact on stimulating learning motivation and improving learning performance, and makes learning content easier to understand. These findings highlight the importance of integrating multimedia teaching aids into educational practice activities to promote students' active participation and sustained motivation in the learning process. Overall, multimedia teaching aids are widely adopted in the field of education because of the many benefits it brings. However, most studies have focused on older students or higher education, and research on younger students in China, especially primary school students, is still limited. Due to

the advanced cognitive skills of older students, methods such as extensive surveys and controlled studies tend to be effective for them. On the other hand, primary school students may lack the cognitive maturity required for complex survey instruments or prolonged experiments. Therefore, simpler questionnaires or brief observation periods could be more suitable for capturing learning motivation among younger students. This creates an essential need to explore how different multimedia teaching aids influence the learning motivation of Chinese primary school students, utilizing approaches that are compatible with their cognitive and emotional growth stages.

2.3 The effectiveness of different types of multimedia teaching aids in teaching

Multimedia technology tools integrate various media formats to build a rich and interesting learning environment for students. Adekunle et al. (2019) believed that televisions, projectors and computers are the main multimedia devices, which enrich teachers' teaching experience and enhance learning and memory. Many studies (Akinoso, 2020; Bulut, 2019; Budiman, 2016; Ulery et al., 2020; Ilhan & Oruç, 2016) have shown that the multi-sensory stimulation and interactivity provided by multimedia tools enable students to better absorb knowledge, thereby improving their learning motivation and academic performance. Gartika et al. (2019) found that interactive multimedia tools created a dynamic and engaging learning environment, fostering both interactivity and collaborative learning. Ghanizadeh & Razavi (2015) found through group experimental that students who use multimedia teaching aids show enhanced academic achievement and are more inclined toward mastery-focused learning goals. Furthermore, in order to evaluate the impact of multimedia technology tools such as computers, calculators, and audio-visual tools, the research results of Lauc et al. (2020) showed that multimedia tools can help teachers monitor students' motivation level and enhanced students' engagement and independent learning abilities.

While multimedia technology tools provide students a wealth of learning resources, their practical implementation faces considerable challenges. Quantitative methods like surveys and pre-tests can provide useful data on overall trends and

outcomes, yet they often overlook students' subjective experiences, such as their feelings about using the tool or changes in motivation throughout the learning process. Although interviews and classroom observations provide valuable insights into students' emotional and behavioral responses, they are often limited by smaller sample sizes, reducing generalizability. Lu'luilmaknun et al. (2021) suggested that incorporating empirical evidence can help address these research limitations, offering a more thorough evaluation of multimedia teaching aids' effectiveness.

Moreover, some studies (Ibe & Abamuche, 2019; Ho & Intai, 2017) have confirmed that audio-visual aids, including video and audio, capture students' attention more effectively than traditional text, particularly when dealing with complex concepts. These tools enhance students' understanding, memory, and overall academic performance.

Compared with traditional methods, multimedia teaching not only increases student engagement but also enhances learning outcomes through diverse and interactive teaching tools (Puspitarini & Hanif, 2019). For example, using digital tools can significantly improve students' vocabulary skills while also increasing student engagement and motivation (Asikkan, 2023). Digital stories not only increase interest in learning, but also promote knowledge acquisition by combining learning content with daily life examples (Basar, 2022). Lin et al. (2017) also paid attention to digital teaching. Through experimental comparison, they found that digital learning can improve learning, optimize learning motivation and learning outcomes.

So, how to stimulate students' curiosity and enthusiasm for knowledge and enhance the absorption and application of knowledge through interactive and gamified teaching methods. A large number of existing studies have extensively discussed it. Arzmann et al. (2023) compared game-based teaching with traditional teaching. The results showed that the fun and competitive nature of gamified learning tools can stimulate students' interest in learning, and the reward mechanism can encourage students to participate in learning more actively. (Hugerat et al., 2020; Kalay & Arikan, 2023).

2.4 Findings

From the existing relevant literature, many researchers have revealed the following key findings through investigations into the impact of multimedia teaching aids on students' learning motivation.

1. Improve student participation and motivation

Multimedia teaching aids, such as video, audio, and interactive whiteboards, have been proven to be effective in grabbing students' attention and increasing their motivation to learn. Studies have indicated that audiovisual tools are particularly good at simplifying complex concepts, helping students better understand and remember content. This advantage is to enhance students' motivation to actively participate in learning activities.

2. Differential effects on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation

The use of multimedia teaching aids has a positive influence both students' intrinsic motivation (interest-driven) and extrinsic motivation (reward-driven). Numerous studies revealed that multimedia tools foster intrinsic motivation by creating an interactive and visually engaging learning environment, while also boosting extrinsic motivation by fulfilling students' desire for achievement and acknowledgment. This combined effect highlights the extensive potential of multimedia tools to enhance student motivation comprehensively.

3. Effectiveness of different types of multimedia teaching aids

The effectiveness of different types of multimedia teaching aids on students differs according to the specific type of tool used. Interactive and gamified resources are particularly impactful due to their competitive elements and rewarding features, which captivate student interest and encourage active engagement. Conversely, visual tools like projectors and videos are better suited for presenting information that is difficult to understand through traditional text. This highlights the need for educators to select multimedia tools that align with their specific teaching objectives and address students' unique learning requirements.

4. Enhance learning effects through multi-sensory stimulation

In the teaching and learning process, the integration of multimedia teaching aids is related to the improvement of academic performance. Studies have found that multi-sensory stimulation provided through multimedia teaching aids helps students better absorb and retain knowledge. Evidence showed that interactive tools not only promote student engagement but also facilitate collaborative learning, leading to higher academic achievement.

These findings provide a basis for exploring the specific impact of multimedia teaching aids on Chinese primary school students' learning motivation and lay the foundation for identifying gaps in current research.

2.5 Gaps or deficiencies in existing research

Educators can effectively use multimedia teaching aids to improve the learning environment, increase students' interest and motivation, and promote their knowledge growth and learning motivation. While these studies collectively affirm the usefulness of multimedia teaching aids and provide valuable insights, there are problems and limitations that point to the need for future research. The statistical analysis of many studies is valuable, but may overlook insights into students' subjective experiences and perceptions. In addition, there is often a lack of differentiation of the impact of different types of multimedia tools, leading to a generalized understanding that does not take into account the different effects of different multimedia tools on learning motivation. Moreover, many studies have focused on senior students, and there is relatively little research on the influence of multimedia teaching aids on the motivation of Chinese primary school students. Therefore, there is still room for further exploration in these areas. First of all, it is necessary to focus on the reaction and use effect of Chinese primary school students when using multimedia tools. Second, a detailed categorized study of the effects of different multimedia tools is needed to provide a deeper understanding of which multimedia teaching aids have the most effective impact on learning motivation.

This study investigated and evaluated the use of multimedia teaching aids in primary school education, focusing on the practical effectiveness of these tools in

increasing learning motivation and their positive impact on academic performance. Through in-depth research on individual differences among students and the long-term effectiveness of these tools, we confirmed the effectiveness of multimedia teaching aids in improving learning outcomes, determined their scope of influence, and analyzed their role in improving the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of primary school students.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

Integrating multimedia teaching aids into teaching can improve primary school students' learning motivation by promoting interaction and cooperation. In order to explore the specific impact of multimedia teaching aids on learning motivation, and how different multimedia teaching aids affect students' learning performance and motivation. The conceptual framework of this study focuses on the direct relationship between multimedia teaching aids and learning motivation, aiming to reveal the role of multimedia teaching aids on learning motivation in primary education.

The framework is based on social constructivism theory, which believes that learning is constructed in social interactions. Students are better able to internalize knowledge through collaboration and communication with peers and teachers. Multimedia teaching aids can enhance students' learning interest and participation through rich visual and interactive experiences, thereby stimulating learning motivation.

In this framework (see figure2.1), multimedia teaching aids directly affect students' learning motivation. Learning motivation includes intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and task value. These motivation factors jointly promote positive academic performance and higher engagement, ultimately improving overall learning outcomes.

In order to quantify the impact of multimedia teaching aids on learning motivation, this study collected data through questionnaire, focusing on students' experience of using multimedia teaching aids and their motivation changes in learning activities. By analyzing questionnaire and experimental data, this study identified the

most effective multimedia teaching aids to improve students' motivation and academic performance, and provided data support for the application of social constructivism theory in actual teaching.

Figure 2.1: The Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study used quantitative research design to collect numerical data and statistical information on the relationship between multimedia teaching aids and learning motivation, including the use of multiple multimedia teaching aids, changes in students' intrinsic and extrinsic learning motivation, and students' experience feedback in using multimedia teaching aids to analyze various changes in learning motivation.

Quantitative research can collect large-scale data and explore the connection between the interaction of multimedia teaching aids and learning motivation through statistical analysis to form clear, measurable conclusions (Taherdoost, 2022). The research quantitatively analyzed the specific effect of multimedia teaching aids in stimulating learning motivation through questionnaire and experimental design.

3.2 Sampling

In order to ensure statistical validity and experimental design needs, this study selected 144 primary school students aged 9 to 12 years from Anhui Province, China, taking into account grade, region, educational background, time, and resources. To ensure that the research results have sufficient statistical validity, the sample size can provide sufficient data support and detect the impact of multimedia teaching aids on students' learning motivation. According to existing research, usually at least 30 students per group are required to participate in the experiment in order to conduct a valid statistical analysis to compare differences between groups. Therefore, this study set a sample size of 144 students to ensure the validity and reliability of the data.

This study adopted cluster sampling to randomly select 144 students from classes 1-4 of fifth grade at Huaibei Meiyuan School as the research subjects. Among them, 77 were boys, accounting for 53.5% of the research subjects. There were 67 girls, accounting for 46.5% of the research subjects. The research subjects were aged 9 to 12 years old, with 136 subjects being mainly 11 years old, accounting for 94.4% of the total number. Among them, there are 5 and 3 people aged 10 and 12 years old, accounting for 3.5% and 2.1% respectively (see Table 3.1). The selected students have similar educational backgrounds and learning environments, which means that the teaching resources and environmental influences on the students are relatively consistent, which helps to reduce interfering variables, so that changes in learning motivation are mainly attributed to differences in teaching methods rather than other external factors. This makes the sample representative and enhances the broad applicability of the research results.

Table 3.1: Gender and age distribution of participants

	Variable	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	77	53.5
	Female	67	46.5
Age	9 years old	0	0
	10 years old	5	3.5
	11 years old	136	94.4

12 years old	3	2.1
Total	144	100

3.3 Instruments

This study used questionnaire (see Appendix C) and experimental design as the main tools.

3.3.1 Questionnaire

A total of 144 students participated in the questionnaire survey. The questionnaire was used to evaluate three dimensions of learning motivation, including intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and task value. The questionnaire survey was conducted twice: once as a pre-test before the experimental intervention and once as a post-test after the intervention. The pre-test was used to measure the baseline level of students' learning motivation before being exposed to multimedia teaching aids. The post-test was used to assess changes in learning motivation after the experimental intervention. The questionnaire used Likert scale to measure students' perception and motivation level of multimedia teaching aids, and convert usage experience and subjective feelings into quantitative data for analysis.

3.3.2 Experimental Research

The 144 students were divided into 4 groups of 36 students each. Each group used different types of multimedia teaching aids, such as video, audio, interactive whiteboards, and gamified learning tools. To ensure consistency, all groups received the same instructional content for two weeks. Pre-test and post-test questionnaires were conducted before and after the experimental intervention to collect data on students' learning motivation. The changes in learning motivation of each group of students between pre-test and post-test were analyzed through paired sample t-test, and the differences in learning motivation between groups were compared to determine the most effective multimedia teaching tools.

3.3.3 Pilot Study

The purpose of this pilot study is to test the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, ensure that the design of the research instrument is scientific and

effective, and lay the foundation for formal data collection. The test subjects were 35 fifth-grade students from Huaibei Meiyuan School. One of them was invalid and 34 were valid questionnaires. The specific implementation steps of this pilot study are as follows:

1. Distribute questionnaires to participating students.
2. Collect and verify students' questionnaire feedback and eliminate invalid questionnaires.
3. Use SPSS software to analyze the reliability and validity of the data.

The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire.

Table 3.2: Reliability Statistics (Overall and Three Dimensions)

Measure	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Overall Questionnaire	0.952	12
Dimension 1 (Intrinsic)	0.922	4
Dimension 2 (Extrinsic)	0.862	4
Dimension 3 (Task Value)	0.859	4

As can be seen from Table 3.2, the overall reliability of the questionnaire is Cronbach's Alpha = 0.952, indicating that the internal consistency of the questionnaire is high. Dimension 1 (intrinsic motivation): Cronbach's Alpha = 0.922, each item has a high correlation with the overall, and the reliability is strong. Dimension two (extrinsic motivation): Cronbach's Alpha = 0.862, the measurement results have high reliability; Dimension three (task value): Cronbach's Alpha = 0.859, the reliability reaches a satisfactory level.

Table 3.3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Measure	Value
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.899
Bartlett's Test (Chi-Square)	321.021
df	66
Sig.	< 0.001

Validity was assessed by KMO and Bartlett's test of sphericity. Table 3.3 shows that $KMO = 0.899$, Bartlett's test of sphericity: $\chi^2 = 321.021$, $df = 66$, $p < 0.001$, indicating that the data are suitable for factor analysis.

After reliability and validity testing, two questions were slightly adjusted to improve the clarity and applicability of the questions. In summary, the questionnaire has good reliability and validity and is suitable for data collection in formal research. The pilot study provided an important reference for the validity of the research tool. By adjusting and optimizing the questions, the reliability and validity of the questionnaire were further improved.

3.4 Data Collection

The data collection process(see Figure3.1) was divided into two stages:

Stage 1: Pre-test

Before the experimental intervention, all 144 students were required to complete the pre-test questionnaire to measure their baseline levels of learning motivation, including intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and task value. Baseline data established a reference point for comparing changes after experimental intervention.

Stage 2: Post-test

After the two-week experimental intervention, all students were required to complete the same questionnaire as a post-test. The post-test captured any changes in students' learning motivation after using different multimedia teaching aids. Statistically analysis was performed on the data collected in two stages to evaluate:

1. Changes in learning motivation within each group (pre-test vs. post-test) using paired sample t-test.
2. Differences in learning motivation outcomes between the 4 groups to identify the most effective multimedia teaching aids.

Stage 1: Pre-test

| |
144 students complete the first questionnaire to establish baseline data on learning motivation

Figure 3.1: Data Collection Process

3.5 Data Analysis

This study aimed to collect questionnaire data from primary school students and their motivations for learning English. This study used descriptive analysis to analyze and evaluate the relationship between multimedia teaching aids and students' learning motivation, and applied comparative analysis to distinguish motivation differences before and after the application of multimedia teaching aids. Through the above analysis, this study summarized the frequency and type of students' use of multimedia teaching aids, as well as the basic situation of their learning motivation scores. This not only helps to understand the overall distribution and trend of the data, but also deeply explores the significant differences between groups, providing empirical basis for subsequent research.

Data analysis was proceeded in the following steps (see Appendix D):

1. Data sorting: Organized and cleaned all collected data before actual analysis. Variables such as frequency and type of use of multimedia teaching aids in the questionnaire were coded into numerical form. Learning motivation data was generated through questionnaires, including three dimensions: intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and task value. These data were entered into SPSS statistical software for analysis.

2. Descriptive statistics: Analyzed the overall trend of the data, including the average value of students' frequency, type and learning motivation scores of multimedia teaching aids, the standard deviation of each variable, and the frequency distribution of the use of multimedia teaching aids.

3. Paired sample t-test: Conducted a paired sample t-test on the learning motivation scores of each group of students before and after the experimental intervention to evaluate the changes in learning motivation within the group. Differences in learning motivation among the four experimental groups were compared to determine the most effective type of multimedia teaching aids.

4. Data visualization: Used charts and graphs to present different frequency of use multimedia teaching aids, and compared students' scores on different dimensions of learning motivation into groups.

5. Result interpretation: based on the mean, standard deviation and frequency distribution results, initially explained the use of multimedia teaching tools and the overall situation of students' learning motivation. By analyzing the frequency of tool use and the overall distribution of students' learning motivation scores, it was possible to initially infer which type of multimedia teaching aids were most effective in stimulating learning motivation.

3.6 Ethical Consideration

Research ethics are the moral norms that must be observed throughout the research process to ensure the fairness and integrity of the research process and results. It involves protecting the rights and interests of participants, such as informed consent and privacy protection. Therefore, researchers must remain highly alert to potential ethical issues. During the data collection process, all relevant ethical practices were fully implemented and maintained.

This study designed and used an informed consent form(see Appendix A&B), and informed consent was obtained from students and their teachers before participating in the study, informing them of the purpose of the study, their right to withdraw, and the confidentiality of their data. This consent form was distributed to participants and

signed by all participants to ensure their informed and voluntary participation in the data collection process. All data were stored securely and used for research only.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Effectiveness of Different Multimedia Teaching Aids

Table 4.1: The average scores of the pre-test and post-test of the four groups in the three dimensions

Group	Dimension	Pre-test Mean	Post-test Mean	Mean Difference
Video	Intrinsic Motivation	3.1597	3.4792	-0.31944
Video	Extrinsic Motivation	2.9653	3.4097	-0.44444
Video	Task value	3.1181	3.6389	-0.52083
Audio	Intrinsic Motivation	2.6667	2.9236	-0.25694
Audio	Extrinsic Motivation	3.2917	3.1111	0.18056
Audio	Task value	2.6736	2.3403	0.33333
Interactive	Intrinsic Motivation	3.0278	3.7361	-0.70833
Interactive	Extrinsic Motivation	2.9931	3.6806	-0.6875
Interactive	Task value	3.0208	3.7986	-0.77778
Game	Intrinsic Motivation	2.9931	3.0347	-0.04167
Game	Extrinsic Motivation	3.2014	3.0417	0.15972
Game	Task value	3.0764	3.1319	-0.05556

Table 4.1 presents the data about the pre-test and post-test mean and mean difference across the four groups. Based on the table, the results indicate that interactive whiteboards show the most significant improvement in all dimensions ($\Delta = 0.708333$, $\Delta = 0.6875$, $\Delta = 0.77778$). Video tools also show significant positive effects in three dimensions ($\Delta = 0.31944$, $\Delta = 0.44444$, $\Delta = 0.52083$), while audio tools ($\Delta = 0.25694$, $\Delta = -0.18056$, $\Delta = -0.33333$) and game tools ($\Delta = 0.04167$, $\Delta = -0.15972$, $\Delta = 0.05556$) have a small or even negative impact on all dimensions.

Through comparative analysis of data, it was determined that the interactive whiteboard significantly enhances learning motivation. This beneficial impact is primarily manifested in the capability of interactive tools to foster an engaging educational environment, boost students' enthusiasm for learning and curiosity, and motivate students to actively engage in classroom activities. Furthermore, interactive whiteboards facilitate a deeper comprehension of learning content and increase

students' recognition of the significance of learning by promoting immediate interaction and collaboration between educators and learners. This interaction not only enhances classroom participation, but also develops students' team awareness and collaboration abilities through cooperative learning, which further enhances their intrinsic and extrinsic learning motivation.

At the same time, video tools have also been shown to have positive effects in improving the perceived task value. The strongest advantage of video tools is that they can present complex educational content in a clear and intuitive way, making the abstract more concrete, thereby helping students to comprehend and remember with it easier. The visual impact of video tools makes learning more engaging, which is especially beneficial for learners with a visual kind of learning preference. By integrating images, animations, and narration, video tools can effectively communicate information and heighten students' interest, further increasing the importance of learning tasks.

These findings support the hypotheses of the research that interactivity and visual tools are, without doubt, more effective in enhancing learning motivation than other forms of multimedia teaching aids. This highlights the need to emphasize interactivity and visual appeal in developing educational resources as an important approach toward enhancing students' motivation. In this regard, teachers will be in a better position to effectively respond to students' learning needs and create a rather more active and stimulating learning environment.

Nevertheless, audio tools did not demonstrate significant effects concerning the improvement of learning motivation, and thus might reflect the limitation of the current theoretical framework to explain the effectiveness of such tools. While audio tools are believed to have the ability to enhance memorization and make things easier to understand in certain learning environments, their effectiveness is likely to be lost without the presence of visual and hands-on aspects, thus becoming ineffective in meeting the learning needs of students. This statement is more applicable to younger students, because for them, mere auditory stimulation is usually not enough to attract their attention and hold it. This limitation makes it even more necessary to rely on

integrated multimedia tools. The findings of Ho & Intai (2017) are diametrically opposed to this view, They noted that audio aids support students in improving their comprehension and retention skills. From this, it could be established that the actual effects of the audio resources perhaps vary based on environmental changes and individual personality, hence requiring more research and confirmation.

In addition, the low impacts of gamified tools contrasts sharply with the high impact gamified learning has on motivation development, as revealed by the study results of Arzmann et al. (2023). The difference can be explained by the fact that the gamified tools used in this study were designed primarily for entertainment and did not fully comply with the core principles of gamified learning. Within the experimental design of this study, the gamified tool placed a strong emphasis on extrinsic motivational factors while being not fully able to encapsulate the specific educational objectives within the game.

This trend may lead students to focus on the game itself rather than learning or skill development through their interaction with these games. The case proves the importance of well-embedding educational objectives into gaming interactions in developing gamified educational resources. For example, the tasks and rewards within the game should be closely connected to the learning material. While completing the game challenges, students can also have an in-depth understanding of knowledge points and enhance the learning experience. In addition, designers also need to pay attention to the balance of game content, not only to maintain the fun of the game, but also to ensure that it is educational, so as to achieve the ideal effect of entertaining and educating. This revelation not only provides a direction for improving the design of gamified tools, but also further illustrates the basic principles that educational technology needs to follow when integrating innovative tools, that is, always taking learning effects as the core goal.

Combining the above data shows that interactive whiteboards are the most effective tool to improve primary school students' learning motivation, followed by video tools. Interactive whiteboards inject new vitality into classroom teaching with their high interactivity and dynamics. Through real-time teacher-student interaction,

instant feedback and diversified display of content, students' interest in learning is greatly stimulated and their sense of participation and belonging is enhanced. Interactive whiteboards can also present complex learning content in the form of charts, animations and videos, making abstract concepts more intuitive and easy to understand, thereby enhancing the value of learning tasks. Video tools display learning content in a visual form, making knowledge transfer more vivid and interesting. This visual reinforcement not only helps students become interested in learning content, but also helps them realize the practical significance of what they are learning.

4.2 Specific Impact on Learning Motivation and Outcomes

Table 4.2: Statistical test results of four groups on learning motivation in three dimensions

Group	Dimension	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Video	Intrinsic Motivation	-1.506	35	0.141
Video	Extrinsic Motivation	-2.007	35	0.052
Video	Task value	-2.275	35	0.029
Audio	Intrinsic Motivation	-1.311	35	0.199
Audio	Extrinsic Motivation	0.781	35	0.44
Audio	Task value	1.784	35	0.083
Interactive	Intrinsic Motivation	-3.42	35	0.002
Interactive	Extrinsic Motivation	-3.2	35	0.003
Interactive	Task value	-5.075	35	<0.001
Game	Intrinsic Motivation	-0.198	35	0.845
Game	Extrinsic Motivation	0.647	35	0.522
Game	Task value	-0.25	35	0.804

Table 4.2 shows the data regarding the magnitude and direction of the mean difference between pre-test and post-test for different multimedia teaching aids, as well as the statistical significance of the mean difference. Based on this table, the data shows that the interactive whiteboard has significant improvements in intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and task value ($t = -3.42$, $t = -3.2$, $t = -5.075$, $p = 0.002$, $p = 0.003$, $p < 0.001$). Video tools only have a significant effect on task value ($t = -2.275$, $p = 0.029$). Audio and gaming tools have no significant impact on each dimension.

These data mean that interactive whiteboards have a significant positive impact on all three dimensions of learning motivation. These tools bring with them unique dynamics and interactive characteristics that heavily induce collaborative learning among the students, increase their enthusiasm for learning, and enhance their initiative and engagement in class. The argument is in agreement with findings from Lauc et al. (2020), which again confirms the vital role of interactive whiteboards in multimedia teaching. In addition, the interactive whiteboard contains a lot of educational resources, such as digital textbooks, animations, diagrams, and videos, which enriches the content taught in the classroom and makes it easier for students to understand difficult ideas. Simultaneously, immediate engagement permits students to engage fully in learning activities, from answering questions or working on their projects to anything involving interaction. This will yield a better-learning process. Moreover, such a mutual interactive process is very helpful in enhancing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to learn among the students.

Video tools have shown great potential in increasing the perceived value of tasks. Visual tools support students' understanding and memory by making clear complex learning materials. For example, animated demonstration and visual stories can turn theoretical notions into real-life scenarios, which help learners build a knowledge framework and increase their perception of how relevant the academic content is to them. The multimedia characteristics of video also make it equally beneficial for reviewing and consolidating information. Students can engage with the video multiple times to deepen their grasp of the curriculum. Nevertheless, video tools exhibit limitations in terms of interactivity, which may hinder their capacity to foster intrinsic motivation; however, they remain an indispensable resource in aiding students to augment the value of their educational endeavors. Students can watch the video repeatedly to deepen their understanding of the course content. However, video tools are relatively weak in interactivity, which may limit their improvement in intrinsic motivation, but it is still a tool that cannot be ignored in helping students improve the value of learning tasks.

In contrast, the impact of audio and gamified tools shows a negative or limited

trend, showing certain limitations. The single sensory stimulation of audio tools lacks visuals or interactivity, which can make it difficult for students to focus or receive immediate feedback during learning. For example, audio content appears relatively boring and cannot meet students' needs for diverse learning experiences. While audio tools may be advantageous in certain learning situations, such as language listening training, they are less effective than interactive whiteboards and video tools in overall improving motivation.

Likewise, gamified tools fail to live up to expectations. Although gamified teaching is generally considered to be significantly engaging and engaging, this study failed to fully integrate learning objectives in the experimental design, thus weakening the educational function of the gamified tools. Additionally, the short experimental period of two weeks may not be sufficient for students to fully adapt to the use of gamified tools or to derive long-term learning benefits from them. Short-term learning behavior may be driven more by the entertainment of the tool rather than the improvement of deep learning motivation. Therefore, in order to optimize the application effect of audio and gamified tools, when designing teaching content, learning tasks should be integrated into games to increase interest and motivate students. This will help better motivate students to learn and enhance the educational value of such tools.

These results also reveal how interactive and video tools specifically impact learning motivation and learning outcomes. First, it positively influences the use of interactive whiteboards and video on interest in English language learning, self-efficacy, and perceived significance among primary school students. The use of interactive whiteboards for presenting instructional content in the classroom is found to be especially effective in meeting the cognitive developmental needs of young students. Such technology can present learning content in a dynamic way, hence making students curious and encouraging them to become actively involved in the learning process. This student-centered interaction model can raise their intrinsic motivation substantially. Moreover, interactive whiteboards support teacher-student engagement through cooperative reward, such as immediate feedback on group

assignments or motivational incentives for class achievements, further increasing student engagement. Such multidimensional interaction not only upgrades the extrinsic motivation of the students but also assures a general dynamic and effectiveness of the learning atmosphere.

Second, video tools have lower interactivity. However, they can help students better understand the learning objectives and increase the perceived value of tasks since they provide students with visually attractive learning material. Via animation, scenario simulation, and visual interpretation, videos can make abstract ideas tangible, thus making it easier for students to develop an understanding of knowledge. Moreover, video content can greatly help in increasing the interest of students toward learning; hence, they find it much easier to concentrate on learning. Video tools are very suitable for students in primary schools, especially in the learning contents that need watching more than once, so as to enable them to further solidify the knowledge that they have learned by repeated viewings. This increase in task value can help students realize the importance of learning, which will enhance their motivation to learn.

Taken together, these findings emphasize the prominent role of interactive whiteboards and video tools in improving primary school students' learning motivation and learning outcomes, and provide necessary reference and guidance for educators to select and design multimedia teaching aids.

4.3 Differences in Influence Between Multimedia Teaching Aids

Table 4.3 Comparative differences in learning motivation among the four groups in three dimensions

Group	Most effective dimension	Mean Difference	t	Sig.(2-tailed)	least effective dimension	Mean Difference	t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Video	Task value	-0.52083	-2.275	0.029	Intrinsic	-0.31944	-1.506	0.141
Audio	No significant	-0.25694	-1.311	0.199	Extrinsic	0.18056	0.781	0.44

Interactive	all dimensions	-0.77778	-5.075	<0.001	No	-	-	-
Game	No significant	-0.04167	-0.198	0.845	all dimensions	-0.05556	-0.25	0.804

Table 4.3 shows the difference in data results regarding the most effective and ineffective dimensions of different multimedia teaching aids. Based on this table, among the four groups of tools, the interactive whiteboard has the most significant improvement in each dimension, and the most effective dimension is task value ($\Delta = 0.77778$, $t = -5.075$, $p < 0.001$). The video tool is moderately effective, with the most effective dimension being task value ($\Delta = -0.52083$, $t = -2.275$, $p = 0.029$) and the least effective dimension being intrinsic motivation ($\Delta = -0.31944$, $t = -1.506$, $p = 0.141$). Audio does not show significant effects in all dimensions, with extrinsic motivation performing the worst ($\Delta = 0.18056$, $t = 0.781$, $p = 0.44$). Gamified tool does not show significant effects in all dimensions, with task value performing the worst ($\Delta = -0.05556$, $t = -0.25$, $p = 0.804$).

These results show that there are significant differences in the effectiveness of different multimedia tools in enhancing learning motivation, with interactive whiteboards showing the most significant improvements in all three dimensions of learning motivation. This tool enhances the dynamism and creativity of pedagogical activities because of its high interactivity and adaptability. For example, interactive whiteboards are able to connect with plenty of educational materials such as digital textbooks, illustrations, photographs, and video contents that enrich the learning environment, allowing learners to understand difficult subjects in an easier manner. It further integrates multimedia into the learning environment, thereby increasing the level of student engagement and catering to the diverse educational needs of learners, which ideally fosters the effective transmission of knowledge.

Interactive whiteboards can offer students more opportunities for participation in class activities, thanks to the special features of real-time interaction. Students can answer questions, ask questions, or even provide their opinions directly on the whiteboard. Teachers are able to adjust learning materials and methods of teaching instantly due to students' responses, so this provides immediate tailored support for students. The mutual interaction between teachers and students helps to minimize the

gap between them and at the same time increases students' motivation to learn and their self-confidence in their ability to study. It is worth noting that the content retention ability of the interactive whiteboard is a considerable advantage. Students can have access and review instructional resources at their own pace, which plays a critical role in knowledge consolidation and transfer. This degree of interactivity allows students to become much more involved in the learning process, which dramatically enhances intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and perceived value of the task.

Their application in learning tasks is of substantial consequence on perceived value. On the other hand, their effect on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation shows rather small and non-significant effects. To some extent, this may stem from the given one-way characteristic of the video presentation without the two-way interaction and spontaneous feedback that were presumed important to create a richer engagement. Most of the video tools explain complex ideas by using animations, situational simulations, or visual imagery, which helps students understand and retain information related to the subject. This teaching method is particularly useful for conveying material that needs to be intuitively grasped and significantly enhances the perceived value of the task. However, the non-interactive nature of video tools limits their potential in increasing students' engagement and classroom participation. The lack of interactivity might let students take on the passive mode in their interaction with the videos, hence negating their potential to gainfully utilize their eagerness to make the learning exercise a success.

The comparative analysis shows that interactivity is a significant aspect of including in any multimedia teaching tool, which is also supported by the studies of Gartika et al. (2019) and Lauc et al. (2020) , their studies showed that the incorporation of interactivity into educational multimedia resources has great potential to improve students' involvement and motivation toward learning. The findings suggest that interaction enhances effective communication between teachers and students, fosters deeper engagement of students with the instructional material, and promotes collaborative learning among peers, which creates a more active and

engaging educational environment. More specifically, interactive whiteboards, characterized by their dynamic and multifunctional features, have emerged as representative exemplars of the tremendous integration of interactivity with instructional content, and the positive reviews received have affirmed the influence of interaction on learning outcomes.

The findings provide additional evidence in support of the high applicability of the theory of social constructivism within educational contexts. This theoretical model holds that learning is a knowledge-creation process in which students actively participate and engage in social interactions. In this paradigm, the beneficial effects of interactive whiteboards are highly confirmed. The interactive whiteboards foster active expression and collaborative participation among the students in the classroom environment; they not only increase the initiative of students in the knowledge construction process but also offer more opportunities for social interaction.

Unexpectedly, the experimentally verified results contradicted previous studies. Even though gamified learning tools are often used to enhance the motivation of students, this study shows that the effectiveness of gamified tools is strongly related to their good design and suitability for educational objectives. If the design of gamified tools is too entertainment-oriented and ignores the integration of learning goals, its actual effect on improving learning motivation may be very limited. Therefore, the design of gamified tools needs to find a balance between entertainment and education.

Overall, these findings not only highlight the central role of interactivity in multimedia teaching tools, but also emphasize the importance of theoretical guidance in educational technology design. By combining the core principles of social constructivism theory and drawing on successful cases from practical research, educators and designers can better develop and optimize multimedia teaching tools to maximize their positive impact on learning motivation and learning effectiveness.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study deeply explored the impact of multimedia teaching tools

on Chinese primary school students' learning motivation and found that different types of multimedia teaching aids have significant differences in improving learning motivation. Interactive whiteboards are the most effective multimedia tools, because it allow a lot of interaction and participation. This helps students feel more motivated and see the value in their tasks. Video tools can also help by making students see learning tasks as valuable. However, because video tools do not have much interaction and participation, they are not as good at boosting students' motivation. Audio tools have a reduced effect on students' motivation because they lack visual aids and interactivity. Even though audio tools can appeal to some students with sound patterns and language help, their one-way way of presenting information does not strongly inspire students' love for learning. Also, though gamified tools might first be appealing because they are fun, they don't work very well since they do not combine design features with learning goals properly. These findings indicate that the interactive features of the tool, the appearance of the content, and its relation to educational objectives are significant aspects that influence the effectiveness of multimedia educational tools on learning enthusiasm. These insights provide a useful framework for choosing and improving multimedia teaching tools and give important help for practical instructional design.

5.2 Implications and Limitations

The results of this study have had a significant impact on primary education, especially in the field of educational theory and practice in China. Learning motivation is the internal process that inspires and sustains students to carry out learning activities and promotes their behavior toward a certain goal. The most meaningful thing in classroom teaching is the stimulation and cultivation of students' interest in learning. Only by cultivating students' strong interest in learning can students take the initiative to learn and explore, thus continuously promoting learning. Finally, accurately exert the positive effect of learning motivation on multimedia teaching. The research results verify the relationship between learning motivation and multimedia learning effects, that is, stable internal learning motivation and high

external learning motivation opportunities and task value promote learning, and the strengthening of relevant learning motivation will promote learning. After learners with high learning motivation used interactive whiteboards and video tools to learn, their positive emotional values increased significantly, and their performance maintenance and performance improvement were also significantly higher than those of the audio and game learning groups. Therefore, it is very important to incorporate multimedia teaching aids into the classroom environment. Furthermore, this study highlights the ability of these tools to improve the limitations of traditional teaching methods, thus improving the overall quality of education. For educators and educational institutions, these results provide practical insights into optimizing multimedia instruction to meet the diverse needs of primary school students.

The results of this research not only verify the role of interaction and participation in improving learning motivation in social constructivism theory, but also provide important reference for primary school education practice. However, this study also has certain limitations. First, the research object is limited to one region in Anhui Province, which may limit the generalizability of the research results to other regions. Secondly, the research period was short and the long-term impact of multimedia teaching aids on learning motivation was not fully observed. Finally, the study adopted quantitative research methods and analyzed changes in students' learning motivation through questionnaires and experimental data. It failed to fully explore students' subjective experience and perception of multimedia tools, and lacked a qualitative explanation of their reactions.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations can be made to optimize the application of multimedia teaching tools in primary education, while providing references for research and practice in related fields.

Firstly, it is recommended to prioritize the use of interactive whiteboards as core teaching tools. Schools should ensure that teachers are proficient in the use of interactive whiteboards by increasing the popularity of multimedia equipment and

teacher training. In addition, video tools serve as effective supplementary resources that can be used to supplement classroom instruction, especially in explaining complex concepts and reinforcing learning objectives. The use of audio tools and gamified tools needs to be re-evaluated to ensure that their designs are more aligned with instructional goals.

For educators, the results highlight the importance of choosing multimedia tools that promote interactivity and visual engagement. It is recommended that teachers give priority to tools such as interactive whiteboards and videos to improve students' learning motivation, especially in the field of language learning. In addition, when designing and implementing gamified teaching, one should avoid over-reliance on external reward mechanisms and focus on teaching strategies that balance extrinsic motivation and cultivate intrinsic interest, especially for young learners. Future research can further explore the impact of combining multiple tools or based on personal learning preferences on the selection of multimedia tools, or observe the lasting effects of multimedia tools on learning motivation through long-term experiments.

Secondly, education policymakers should increase investment in multimedia teaching resources, especially in rural areas and areas with fewer resources, to promote educational equity. At the same time, teachers are guided to rationally select tools based on course objectives and student characteristics.

Future research should further expand the sample scope, such as covering students from different regions or educational backgrounds, to improve the generalizability of the research results. And explore the long-term effects of multimedia tools and the impact of the combined application of multiple tools on learning motivation and performance. At the same time, we can deeply explore students' subjective experience of multimedia tools through supplementary qualitative data, such as interviews or classroom observations. In addition, research can also explore the potential role of emerging educational technologies such as virtual reality and artificial intelligence, and further enrich the application research of multimedia teaching tools.

Declarations

Author Contribution Statement

The author confirms that they are the sole contributor to this work and is responsible for the design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and writing of the manuscript.

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References

Abdulrahaman, M. D., Фарук, H., Oloyede, A. A., Surajudeen-Bakinde, N. T., Olawoyin, L. A., Mejabi, O. V., Imam-Fulani, Y. O., Fahm, A. O., & Azeez, A. L. (2020). Multimedia tools in the teaching and learning processes: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 6(11), e05312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05312>

Adekunle, S. E., Adewale, O. S., & Boyinbode, O. K. (2019). Appraisal on perceived multimedia technologies as modern pedagogical tools for strategic improvement on teaching and learning. *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science*, 10(8), 15-26. <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijmecs.2019.08.02>

Akinoso, O. (2018). Effect of the use of multimedia on students' performance in secondary school mathematics. *Global Media Journal*, 16(30), 1-8.

<https://www.proquest.com/openview/f5daff788aa2d39f7cfc354aa643f672/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=29638>

Arztmann, M., Hornstra, L., Jeurig, J., & Kester, L. (2023). Effects of games in STEM education: A meta-analysis on the moderating role of student background characteristics. *Studies in Science Education*, 59(1), 109-145. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/03057267.2022.2057732>

Asikcan, M. (2023). Using digital tools to improve vocabulary in fourth-grade primary school students. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 10(3), 801-822. <https://ijcer.net/index.php/pub/article/view/480>

Başar, T. (2022). The effect of digital stories on 3rd graders' achievement, attitudes and motivation in science lesson. *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(5), 127-142. <http://dergipark.org.tr/en/doi/10.17275/per.22.107.9.5>

Blanco, B. M., Ramos, E. Á., Biel, L. A., & Collantes, M. P. (2024). Vademecum of artificial intelligence tools applied to the teaching of languages. *JOTSE*, 14(1), 77-94. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jotse.2522>

Budiman, R. (2016). Developing learning media based on augmented reality (AR) to improve learning motivation. *Journal of Education, Teaching and Learning*, 1(2), 89-94. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/209026/>

Bulut, R. (2019). An analysis of the effects of multimedia teaching on student achievement. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 15(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2019.184.1>

Fajari, L. E. W. (2020). The effect of problem-based learning multimedia and picture media on students' critical-thinking skills viewed from learning motivation and

learning styles in elementary school. *Ilkogretim Online*, 19(3).
<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/322539559.pdf>

Gartika, E., Rahayu, W., & Utomo, E. (2019). Development of interactive mathematics multimedia teaching materials for building space in class v primary schools. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Studies*, 1(5), 467-472. <https://doi.org/10.29103/ijevs.v1i5.1717>

Ghanizadeh, A., & Razavi, A. (2015). The impact of using multimedia in English high school classes on students' language achievement and goal orientation. *International Journal of Research Studies in Educational Technology*, 4(2). <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/151128/>

Ho, D. T. K., & Intai, R. (2017). Effectiveness of audio-visual aids in teaching lower secondary science in a rural secondary school. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educators and Education*, 32, 91-106. <https://doi.org/10.21315/apjee2017.32.7>

Hugerat, M., Kortam, N., Maroun, N. T., & Basheer, A. (2020). The educational effectiveness of didactical games in project-based science learning among 5th grade students. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(10), em1888. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/8490>

Ibe, E., & Abamuche, J. (2019). Effects of audiovisual technological aids on students' achievement and interest in secondary school biology in Nigeria. *Heliyon*, 5(6). [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(18\)34013-1](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(18)34013-1)

Ilhan, G. O., & Oruc, S. (2016). Effect of the use of multimedia on students' performance: A case study of social studies class. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 11(8), 877-882. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1099996>

- Islam, F. S. P. (2020). The use of multimedia and its impact on Bangladeshi EFL learners at tertiary level. *International Journal of Language Education*, 4(1), 150-157. <https://doi.org/10.26858/ijole.v4i2.12150>
- Kalay, A., & Arikan, Y. D. (2023). The effects of gamified instructional material on learners' perceived motivation and academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 6(3), 789-807. <https://doi.org/10.31681/jetol.1353075>
- Lauc, T., Jagodic, G. K., & Bistrovic, J. (2020). Effects of multimedia instructional message on motivation and academic performance of elementary school students in Croatia. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(4), 491-508. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1270661>
- Li, G., Sun, Z., & Jee, Y. (2019). The more technology the better? A comparison of teacher-student interaction in high and low technology use elementary EFL classrooms in China. *System*, 84, 24-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.05.003>
- Lin, M. H., Chen, H. C., & Liu, K. S. (2017). A study of the effects of digital learning on learning motivation and learning outcome. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 13(7), 3553-3564. <https://www.ejmste.com/article/a-study-of-the-effects-of-digital-learning-on-learning-motivation-and-learning-outcome-4843>
- Lu'Luilmaknun, U., Anwar, A., Triutami, T. W., Salsabila, N. H., & Gunawan, G. (2021). Students' responses toward the use of technology learning media in mathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1933(1), 012076). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1933/1/012076>

- Mai, X. (2019). Multimedia technology aids college art teaching research. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1213(4), 042010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1213/4/042010>
- Puspitarini, Y. D., & Hanif, M. (2019). Using Learning Media to Increase Learning Motivation in Elementary School. *Anatolian Journal of Education*, 4(2), 53-60. <https://doi.org/10.29333/aje.2019.426a>
- Rachmavita, F. P. (2020). Interactive media-based video animation and student learning motivation in mathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1663(1), 012040. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1663/1/012040>
- Taherdoost, H. (2022). What are different research approaches? Comprehensive Review of Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method research, their applications, types, and limitations. *Journal of Management Science & Engineering Research*, 5(1), 53-63. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4178694>
- Ulery, A., Smith Muese, A., Carroll, K. C., Chamberlin, B., White, L., Martinez, P., ... & Gleason, J. (2020). Impact of multimedia learning tools in agricultural science classes. *Natural Sciences Education*, 49(1), e20011. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nse2.20011>
- Yu, Z., Yu, L., Xu, Q., Xu, W., & Wu, P. (2022). Effects of mobile learning technologies and social media tools on student engagement and learning outcomes of English learning. *Technology, Pedagogy and Education*, 31(3), 381-398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1475939X.2022.2045215>

Questionnaire: The Impact of Multimedia Teaching Aids on Primary School Students' Learning Motivation in China

Dear student, thank you for participating in this questionnaire. The purpose of this survey is to study the impact of multimedia teaching aids on Chinese primary school students' English learning motivation. Please choose the option that best suits your actual feelings. Your responses will be kept strictly confidential and will be used for research purposes only.

To help you better understand how choices are made in the questionnaire, consider the following example: If the question is: "I like to play games."

- If you like playing games very much, you can select "Strongly Agree" (5 points).
- If you like playing games a bit, you can choose "Agree" (4 points).
- If you don't feel particularly comfortable playing games, you can select "Neutral" (3 points).
- If you don't like playing games very much, you can select "Disagree" (2 points).
- If you don't like playing games at all, you can select "Strongly Disagree" (1 point).

I have read the informed consent form and agree to participate in this study.

Basic Information

1. What is your gender?
Male Female

2. What is your age?
9 years old 10 years old 11 years old 12 years old

Part 1: Intrinsic Motivation

Please select the option that best matches your situation:

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

1. I'm greatly interested in learning English.
- 1 2 3 4 5

2. I find learning more interesting when using multimedia teaching aids.
- 1 2 3 4 5

3. I like the English teaching style in classroom.
- 1 2 3 4 5

4. I can appreciate the original English novels, songs and movies.
- 1 2 3 4 5

Part 2: Extrinsic Motivation

Please select the option that best matches your situation:

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

5. I can pass the English final exam.

- 1 2 3 4 5

6. I can get praise from teachers or rewards like prizes or certificates.

- 1 2 3 4 5

7. I am more motivated to perform better in the English class when I receive awards or recognition.

- 1 2 3 4 5

8. Learning English through multimedia tools helps me understand how useful it is in society.

- 1 2 3 4 5

Part 3: Task Value

Please select the option that best matches your situation:

(1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

9. Learning English is important for my future.

- 1 2 3 4 5

10. The use of multimedia teaching aids helps to make the content clearer and more understandable.

- 1 2 3 4 5

11. English learning helps me broaden my horizons.

- 1 2 3 4 5

12. I have confidence in facing difficulties in the course of learning English.

- 1 2 3 4 5